

MEASURING THE PERFORMANCE OF THE NONPROFIT ORGANIZATION: THE MANAGERIAL RELEVANCE OF THE SOCIAL RETURN ON INVESTMENT FOR MULTI-PROJECT ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of the paper is to investigate the capacity of the Social Return on Investment (SROI) for supplying managerial informational needs in multi-project contexts and the means to integrate the SROI in project management tools for decision-making processes.*

Methodology/approach - *Drawing upon the specifics of SROI from relevant literature, compared with other financial tools, we construe a systematic integration of the SROI methodology into the project management tools.*

Findings – *the proposal to integrate the SROI with the project management, by mediating between the key performance indicators and SROI outcomes; the identification of a SROI-based assessment of project intake decisions; pointing the need to integrate a time factor in SROI estimates.*

Research limitations/implications – *The approach is mainly theoretical requiring practical application through project management procedures.*

Practical implications – *The paper points to practical ways to embed the SROI methodology in project management instruments and to the need for incorporating time constraints into the SROI estimates.*

Originality/value – *The value of the paper consists in the proposal to link the project performance indicators to a SROI sensitivity analysis, reflected by the integration of SROI in the project management tools, and the case for including time factors in the SROI estimates.*

Key words: *Social Return on Investment, Project Management.*

Introduction

The old dictum “there are only costs inside [the organization]” was reflected by the different stages of the measurement “revolution” (Eccles, 1991). In economic sectors with a strong competitive rivalry, the marketing indicators became more significant for the survival of the entities than the financial ones. The category of stakeholders vital to the survival of companies were the customers, hence information about their constituency and preferences became highly relevant. A second wave of the measurement revolution was represented by the system of quality indicators that aimed at defining the products and services through the lenses of the customer’s appraisal (Eccles, 1991).

The diversification of the range for performance indicators has led to the possibility of their ranking and customization according to the organizational strategic objectives. This consequence exhibits a bi-univocal relationship between what is measured and what results are obtained. For nonprofits, managerial strategies are often formulated in terms for which either performance measurement is not possible (in a strategically meaningful fashion) or there are no specific organizational functions able to achieve the measuring.

In the context of this paper, a nonprofit is an organization characterized by a restriction of non-distribution of profits (through dividends or managerial wages) (Anheier and Salamon, 2006). This definition captures various organizational settings under the same umbrella, encompassing the charitable/voluntary sector, non-governmental organizations and civil society organisms. By multi-

project contexts, we mean organizations that supply all their outputs by means of inter-related projects. Hence, multi-project context refers to project based-organizations, portfolios or programs, which cannot be explained in terms of an aggregation of disparate projects.

Financial performance indicators present information that is mainly intended for current or potential capital holders. Even for the shareholders, the financial information is retrospective in nature, allowing for relevant inter-temporal comparisons within the past performance of the same entity or with the current performance of entities (having a similar economic profile of production structure and beneficiaries). For project-based nonprofits, the financial performance indicators the financial results for projects would not represent a profit, but rather a time lag between the accrual accounting imputation of incomes/expense and their cash flows influence. Also, the interests of the donors of a nonprofit are distinct from those that could be captured in financial accounting informing donors requires a different approach, "for if there is no pay check, achievement is the sole reward" (Drucker, 2005).

Unable to benefit from the uniformity of performance information, nonprofits are searching for metrics and communities of practice that will make the results of nonprofit efforts comparable, both in time and space, for various categories of stakeholders. Donors in particular are interested in those entities that can substantiate their results, even though in nonprofits there will always be a tension between moral results (specified in the mission) and allocative or economic results (specified by indicators) (Drucker, 2005). Finding suitable performance indicators would also allow comparing nonprofits in terms of microfinance, assessing organizational and managerial capacity.

The managerial difficulty of measuring the performance of nonprofit organizations is among the peculiarities of these entities. This difficulty influences decision-making practices - from strategy development to current decision-making processes. The fact that, in principle, managerial activity cannot be rewarded in relation to financial performance makes finding adequate indicators even more difficult. This informational need is addressed by creating tools and techniques, by producing a vocabulary and a "grammar" for communities of practitioners, being able to evaluate the results of nonprofits.

Lately, a number of instruments for assessing the social impact of nonprofits and businesses were proposed. These approaches propose an extended organizational ontology that internalizes the outcomes experienced by a multitude of stakeholders (Nichols et al. 2012; PWC, 2013; KPMG, 2014). By capturing outcomes covering social and environmental concerns, these approaches indicate a conceptual transition from organizations depicted as owned by shareholders to entities depicted as owned by communities, as long as the latter are stakeholders in the well-being (or failure) of the entities. In economic language, the performance indicators aim at integrating results, previously seen as externalities.

In multi-project contexts, performance appraisal involves connecting key indicators of achieving project goals with the organization's global performance indicators. When a multi-project nonprofit chooses to implement a methodology for measuring strategic alignment, a rule for deriving indicators from the project-level outputs to the organizational social impact must be in place. Hence, the indicators for work packages must reflect the influence of a certain package on indicators of organizational performance. This implies the judicious alignment of the project objectives with the strategic ones to make possible a methodologically consistent, and spatially comprehensive, measurement of the results.

The aim of this paper consists in exposing the capacity of the Social Return on Investment (SROI) approach to serve the managerial informational needs in multi-project contexts. This relevance is expressed through the suitability of SROI for grounding strategic decisions and current project management issues. One of the claims of the SROI guidance methodology is that it might be used as a managerial instrument. The research question is hence: How can the SROI approach be integrated and embedded in project management tools and practices for sustaining decision-making processes?

The paper analyses the SROI approach through the lenses of project management practices. Drawing upon an inventory of SROI challenges from relevant literature, on the specifics of SROI methodology, compared with other financial tools, we construe a systematic integration (through analogy of different common notions and tools) of the SROI methodology into the project management tools - proposing various means and insights of integration.

The Social Return on Investment – prospects and challenges

The Social Return on Investment (SROI) is a framework for measuring social impact, aiming to achieve a language shared in communities of practice, led by the consistent application of a set of principles. The application of the principles within the SROI may lead to different results, depending on the context of the pursuits whose value is under examination. SROI has its roots in the theory of change, stakeholder theory and cost-benefit analysis. It is aiming at determining a value of social impact, mediated by financial proxies, in order to capture as accurately as possible the net outcome of nonprofit activities. The fundamental difference between the SROI approach and the cost-benefit analysis is given by the explicit integration of as many (relevant) stakeholders as possible in the outcome estimates, this difference in approach being due to the influence of sustainability standards (Nichols, 2017).

While SROI claims to represent an informational device for managerial and stakeholder interests, the authors of the guide do not recommend a direct comparison of nonprofit activities, by using the value of SROI. However, we consider that if a SROI report of comparable activities contains the methodological details and counterfactual assumptions used therein, then, with due professional caution, the SROI values might be compared. To suggest that this is not recommended, would inevitably lead to a tendency for donors not to use it as a tool for benchmarking organizations or selecting projects for available funding. From the SROI perspective, the comparability of outcomes implies the standardization of the conceptual framework and the existence of independent audit bodies for SROI implementation.

SROI could be a retrospective tool, for assessing the outcomes of completed activities, or a forecast tool, predicting the amount of created social value, were the nonprofit activities to meet their intended outcomes. As a performance indicator, SROI determination involves reporting effects to efforts, the stages of SROI implementation seeks from the outset to understand social change from the perspective of stakeholders, in order to obtain elements leading to the financial assessment of effects or outputs (value created) and efforts or inputs (costs). Using a tool called Value Map - embodied in a spreadsheet (Nichols et al. 2012), allows the calculation of the SROI. The completion of this instrument indicates that SROI is determined as a ratio between the present value of outcomes and the present value of the inputs needed to obtain the social impact, as in the equation below (1).

$$SROI = \frac{\text{Present value of outcomes}}{\text{Present value of inputs}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{O_i}{(1+r)^i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{I_i}{(1+r)^i}} \quad (1)$$

Where: - O – financial value of the outcomes; - I – financial value of inputs; - i – year of reference; - r - discounting rate.

This formula is mathematically identical to the financial return on investment, but the means to calculate the financial values of the outputs and inputs differ radically from the financial-accounting way of determining the return on investment. Since for some of the inputs and outcomes (such as - changing the live style of beneficiaries, providing volunteering opportunities etc.) there is no marketable value and financial proxies are to be used as a value substitute. These financial proxies are a reflection of the practitioners' assessment of counterfactual scenarios linked with a certain social outcome.

Another major distinction between SROI and the return on investment for economic projects consists in that the latter can be marketed and sold as investment opportunities (Weber, 2013). Still, on a deeper level, there is a funding market for nonprofit projects, even if the donors do not request the calculation of a forecast SROI for the selection of projects. It can be speculated whether the value of financing represents the price of the project as a process, or the project represents only a mean to obtain the deliverables, which are evaluated through financing.

There are some managerial difficulties in applying the SROI framework in a systematic way – such as (Millar and Hall, 2012; Arvidson et al. 2013): lack of fidelity in rendering the heterogeneity of entities and projects; the need for an organizational data collection system; the precarious nature of the counterfactual estimates necessary for the calculation of the SROI; the expensiveness in terms of dedicated time and trained staff. There are also difficulties of estimation: determining the fixed cost part of the value attributed to the outcomes; choosing a discounting rate; determining the value of voluntary work and its nature as input / output; arbitrariness in decisions on the counterfactual future – through deadweight, dislocation and attribution (Arvidson et al., 2013).

The fact that the volunteers of nonprofits can be seen as both beneficiaries (of trainings) and inputs is also challenging. For some volunteers, volunteering is not equivalent to work, but to spending spare time. When it comes to the difficulty of value attribution, it seems that more is required of SROI than is required from financial indicators, since those also based (in the forecast calculation) on counterfactual assumptions based on professional reasoning alone.

The relevance of the Social Return on Investment in multi-project environments

The position held by the management of nonprofits, as mediators between beneficiaries and donors might be seen from the perspective of the agent theory. Considering the multiple informational asymmetries between these parties, it is necessary to implement a methodology for evaluating social outcomes in a way that could be translated into reports understandable with minimal effort.

In multi-project organizations, the performance indicators associated with the project objectives are usually metrics describing the efficiency of a project from the perspective of a strategic grid - key performance indicators – KPIs. These metrics are required by donors as a way to assess organizational performance. Being required by donors, these indicators reflect the social perspective and interests of these stakeholders. What constitutes significant social change for the donor may appear to have minor social influence from the strategic perspective of the organization’s intent. However, if the requested KPIs are decisive for the social impact of the project in a SROI approach, the degree of compliance with the donors’ requirements will influence the SROI value. At times, the KPIs required by donors show that the beneficiaries were exposed to some factors of social change, rather than indicating a measure of the impact these factors might have.

Trying to integrate the project management approach with the SROI theory of change, we begin with grouping sets of deliverables in work packages having associated indicators. This approach is supplemented, at the work package level, with their impact on the SROI value, as suggested in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Integrating project KPIs with the SROI

The requirements traceability matrix can be extended with information on the KPIs and the SROI sensitivity to KPI’s variance (the sensitivity can be expressed by a factor applied to the attributed value of the outcomes). This correlation shall also be present in the Value Map to draw a formal link between the project requirements and their influence on the SROI. Figure 2. presents the inclusion of these factors in the two aforementioned documents.

Figure 2. Embedding KPI's influence on SROI from the Requirements Traceability Matrix to the Value Map

From the perspective of the project network, the contribution of each project's deliverables to the organizational SROI can be depicted as in Figure 3. where projects denoted A and B, lead to a respective measure of SROI, contributing to the organizational impact - denoted SROI_o.

Figure 3. The contribution of project KPIs to the organizational value of SROI

At operational level, project managers can appreciate the alignment with the project requirements either using a dashboard (reflecting also the donor’s requirements amidst the strategic landscape) or a project health form, which specifies the status of the project in terms of costs, deliverables, risks etc. At the project level, it becomes visible that the role of SROI methodology, as a decision-making tool for managers, prioritizes the management among stakeholders in a manner inconsistent with the apparent neutrality of SROI in terms of stakeholder ranking.

Using a SROI forecast as a strategic tool in multi-project organizations involves: a uniform inter-project procedure for SROI instruments at project level, the construction of a common database for financial proxies, *i.e.* assignment of identical values for identical outcomes; the possibility for weighted aggregation of SROI to obtain a value of organizational SROI, as in relation (2) – already suggested by Figure 3; a sensitivity analysis of SROI at the organizational and project level for KPIs affecting various stakeholders and their associated deliverables.

$$SROI_O = \sum_{p=1}^n k_p SROI_P \quad (2)$$

Where: p - indicative of the project; Kp – the specific strategic weight of SROI for project P

The only influence of time made explicit in SROI consists in discounting the outcomes for multi-annual projects. However, a homogeneous discounting rate does not show a very diverse time preference of the stakeholders. It is challenging to balance an increased time preference for beneficiaries with a fixed short-term productive capacity and time constraints on the available of funding. The efficiency of deadlines in projects implies an increased SROI in multi-project environments. For these reasons the SROI analysis should be done as a function of time (3).

$$SROI = f(t) \quad (3)$$

The financial position will also be affected in time by the acquisition of non-current assets of project restricted usage and their ongoing depreciation. All these time-related issues need to be reflected in the SROI by inclusion in the Value Map.

Conclusions

The aim of the paper was to expose SROI's ability to meet managerial information needs in multi-project contexts. This capacity is shown by the adequacy of the SROI to substantiate strategic decisions and current project management issues. Starting from an inventory of the specifics and limitations of SROI in the relevant literature, on this basis we described a possibility of systematic integration of the SROI methodology in project management tools - proposing means and indicating peculiar difficulties of this endeavor.

The main contributions of the paper are: the proposal to integrate the SROI methodology with the project management tools, by mediating between the key performance indicators (KPIs) and the SROI outcomes indicators, through ongoing stakeholder consultations; the identification of a SROI-based assessment of strategic project-intake decisions; pointing to the need to integrate a time factor in the SROI estimates - for a better expression of the project duration efficiency, the usage of restricted assets and variances in the stakeholders' time preferences.

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